

Survey 2026, the Educational Part

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Abstract

This paper deals with teaching and learning modern Linear Algebra and it elaborates on our most urgent task in Mathematics as a whole, and more specifically, in teaching Linear Algebra to freshmen today.

To be effective, it is time now to create and propagate modern Matrix Theory and Matrix Computation based syllabi. Here we introduce full semester Lesson Plans for first Linear Algebra courses and discuss them.

To prepare our post-Covid students properly, we need to use interactive teaching methods and inversely taught syllabi now.

My Lesson Plans are slowly creating a grass-roots fire among students and catching instructors as well.

This course follows the Teaching Principles of Jean Piaget from 80 years ago who established that we only learn deeply and retain what we need to understand, and not what we are taught in order to pass a test or to graduate.

My modern elementary Linear Algebra course has been designed and class tested. It relies only on three mathematical principles.

The Row Echelon Form Reduction teaches us of the value of pivot searches.

Krylov Vector Iteration allows us to look inside intrinsic matrix qualities such as matrix eigenvectors and eigenvalues.

Both of these rely on Riesz's Theorem on Matrix Representations of Linear Functions in varying vector space bases.

Early on, my students will build their own basic software codes for essential tasks in modern Linear Algebra and they will use computer computations rather than computing by hand.

Students create and improve their own basic algorithmic codes for the essential tasks of modern Linear Algebra throughout the course.

Matrices are used everywhere in the internet, in our cell-phone and computer worlds, and in Engineering, AI, Medicine, Shipping, Traveling, Banking and so forth.

The proposed course achieves deep learning in students of inversely taught classrooms.

Keywords : math history, Linear Algebra, interactive teaching, inverse classroom methods, math education, lesson plans, elementary Linear Algebra, elementary Matrix Computations, Linear Algebra syllabi, deep learning, Piaget Principle, Semmelweis Syndrome, meta-mathematics

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Talk Slides at

<https://webhome.auburn.edu/~uhligfd/Survey2026Edupart.pdf>

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0 : A Detour : A Foreword of Sorts on the Genesis of the slow Matrix Field of Values Discovery from 1907 to 1918

I started the current cluster of my papers in the early 2020s by investigating the early appearances of the concept behind and the actual term "Matrix Fields of Values" in the math literature.

Otto Toeplitz and Felix Hausdorff were the first mathematicians to conceive of and introduce this term into the mathematical literature.

Toeplitz approached this topic at the Berlin Academy and coined the term "Wertbereich"

(note: no plural 'e') in his first invited talk in front of the Academy in 1907. The mathematical language and papers at the time had no such term. Toeplitz developed matrix and convexity computational ideas to plot the boundary curve of that new mathematical 'item' (FOV) concretely.

Another approach came to him from the then popular studies of operator polynomials in Linear Functions in infinite dimensional normed vector spaces. These eventually morphed into the beginnings of Functional Analysis in the middle years of the 1900s. This work was applied by Felix Hausdorff to n dimensional vector sets under Linear Transformations and it lead him to understand the convexity of the FoV for all square matrices.

The mathematics that surround the *historic matrix Field of Values genesis* from the early 1900s are well explained by Leopold Féjer [6] and by Isabelle Bennismon and Kalin Kostadinov in [2].

Henry Minkowski's convex body theorem and proof from around 1900 for $n = 2$ is equally important for understanding the roots of the Matrix Fields of Values, see the survey [3] by Daniel Comeaux.

The operator convexity results were applied to the mapping of vectors in \mathbb{R}^n to their images on the Field of Values boundary. Theoretically the field of values boundary points were then obtainable from the extreme eigenvalue eigenvectors x of A after evaluating the Rayleigh quotient $x^* A x / x^* x \in \mathbb{R}^2$, in the 2-D range plane, acting as our common drawing plane.

All of these works lay the groundwork for Charlie Johnson's final practical computational method for drawing of the Field of Values boundary curve in [14] when effective and accurate matrix eigen-computations had become available in Matrix Numerical Analysis by using John G. F. Francis' QR algorithm [7, 8, 10] and reliable LAPACK codes and software in the mid 1900s.

300 years or more years ago, the relation between the coefficients of various short power series such as Taylor Series, Fourier Series, or algebraic polynomials were scrutinized for their function or mapping properties.

Which truncated leading power series snippets would transfer compact sets in the domain into compact sets in their range space. Such *fundamental questions of compactness, closedness and convexity* seem of great import in much of Mathematics. And these concepts are all *intertwined* since Descartes' or Cardano's times and possibly much earlier, from Aristotle and Archimedes, and their predecessors, and followers, in antiquity and into modern times, - all around the globe.

They involved concepts in *algebra and geometry, analysis and topology, and number theory*. Eventually nascent *matrix theory* was involved after Seki, Leibniz, Cauchy, Gauss, Sylvester, Weierstrass and many others from 1600 through the 1800s. And today *Matrix Theory, Matrix Computations and Matrix Applications* are still being developed further and have had *many uses* in the *expanding engineering work* of the beginning *Industrial Revolution* from the mid 1700s and 1800s in Europe. And likewise in our rapid Engineering advances of the 2000s; and so forth, today and tomorrow – for our *ever increasing human needs*.

These developments lead mathematicians first to the notions of *compact sets* and their preservation under *continuous maps*, then to the concept of *convexity* and the desire to preserve some properties under 'power series snippet mappings'. If a set lay in certain ways in the domain, what was the smallest set in the range space that would contain all snippet images and so forth.

Felix Hausdorff used the field of value boundary point generating algorithm *as his mapping between vectors in \mathbb{R}^n or \mathbb{C}^n and our 2-D plotting plane*, see [11]. His first sentence reads :

"Herr Toeplitz hat in dieser Zeitschrift kürzlich gezeigt¹⁾, dass der Wertvorrat W einer Bilinearform, als Punktmenge in der komplexen Zahlenebene, außen von einer konvexen Kurve begrenzt ist, aber die Frage offen gelassen, ob er das ganze Innere dieser Kurve erfüllt. Es ist nun sehr einfach zu zeigen, daß diese Frage zu bejahen, nämlich W selbst eine konvexe Menge ist." ... "Der Wertvorrat W einer komplexen Matrix C ist, nach Herrn Toeplitz, die Menge der Zahlen w , welche die Form x^*Cx durchläuft wenn ... " $\|x\| = 1$ "Es kommt nun einfach darauf an, daß die Menge M der Wertsysteme ... zusammenhängent ist."

This is then proved by Otto Toeplitz [22] using a theorem of Leopold Féjer [6].

And thus we learned in 1918 that the Field of Values of every square matrix is convex.

These historic *algebraic and analytic*, and *topological and geometric results* paved the way for our *modern numerical Fields of Values studies* and their use in applications from the 1960s through today. They are now built on *software, computers, and numerical computations*.

How to actually *compute the Field of Values boundary curve numerically* was introduced and studied by Charlie Johnson [13, 14] and others only after the *invention of computers* and the development of *mathematical software* from the 1940s into the 1970s.

My cluster results from the early 2020s are all interconnected and intertwined, backwards, forwards and sideways. When trying to draw the directed edge implication graph of this cluster out on paper, the minimal directed graph dimension will require at least three or four dimensions, since one or two dimensions will clearly not suffice.

The cluster results all hinge on newly extended versions of *Matrix Theory* and *Matrix Computations*, developed by the Author and helped along by many others.

The theory behind our new *computational matrix algorithm* is seemingly elementary and uses the *concept of invariant subspaces* for Matlab's `eig` computed 'eigenvectors' or Krylov Vector Iterations of one *flow matrix* $B(t_a)$ to find the *coarsest simultaneous block structure* for all flow matrices $B(t_b)$ with $t_a \neq t_b$. Thus our combined method block-diagonalizes any given matrix flow $A(t)$, or any given static matrix A – as finely as possible, if at all.

Our intended aim in [31] was to discover *unitarily diagonal-block decomposable matrices* and *matrix flows* quickly and *fast and accurate* enough for real world use *in real-time* from *time-varying sensor data*.

The *unitary block decomposition of matrix flows or single square matrices* has not been resolved by algebraic means *in 100 + years* and this has possibly never been tried before, because there *existed no algebraic way or ideas to start from* – before *the advent of computers and Matrix based software*.

Instead, *our new way of testing and establishing unitary decomposability* of a *Matrix* or *Matrix flow* hinges entirely on *numerical algorithms* that decide the issue depending on the *lay of the near zero entries* and of the *sizable ones* in the *associated hermitean Johnson matrix flow*

$$\mathcal{F}(t) = \cos(t)H + \sin(t)K \tag{XXX}$$

for $0 \leq t \leq 2\pi$.

Compare the sketch by von Neumann and Paul Wigner [19, p.469] with our logical 0-1 computational and combinatorial output in [31], Figures 1 through 5 on pages 536 through 541 for matrices with no repeated eigenvalues, and in [31] and Figure 6 on p. 542 for matrices with sizable Jordan blocks or repeated eigenvalues.

As a 'classical' *algebraic proof* of our result has *never been attempted*, we dare to claim that *an algorithmic proof* was actually impossible *before the advent of computers* and a deeper understanding of *matrix flows* such as the *hermitean Johnson flow* $\mathcal{F}(t)$ and the *predictive qualities and accuracy of Zhang Neural Networks*, as brought to light recently in ZNN [36] or AZNN [34].

Albert Einstein shunned this fundamental Quantum Theory problem and rather worked on relativity.

Niels Bohr's group wanted to understand *eigencurve crossings* and their *relation to the unitary matrix block-decomposability of matrices*, see the exploratory plot by von Neumann and Paul Wigner [19, p. 469].

But neither succeeded in solidifying the foundations of Quantum Theory and Quantum Chemistry.

Eigencurve crossing studies for the still un-resolved unitary block-diagonalization problem would begin anew with Charlie Johnson's practical method [14] for constructing the field of values boundary curve in the 1970s and pick up again in the 1990s in Luca Dieci et al.'s papers [4], [5] and in many other papers of Luca's research group, and by others; and in Loisel and Maxwell's paper [17], and in some of my eigencurve papers [26], Chapter 9.1, [29], [30], [31], [37], e. g. .

This continued until around 2020, when several small partial results (maybe 10 to 15 %) of the *unitary block-decomposition problem* had been solved, but no complete classification had been found and the century old *deep fundamental problems* in this introductory write-up were still open in 2023, until [31] appeared in print.

My *final classification of unitary block-decompositions* [31] for both, general matrix flows and static matrices, was ultimately inspired by *Yunong Zhang's parameter-varying Neural Networks* that date back to his doctoral thesis [38] of 2001.

Why spent 4 pages on complicated mathematical results in the introduction to a Math education paper on *early College Math Education* ? And more specifically, in a paper on structuring and teaching the *first Linear Algebra Course* ?

All our Electronic Computers are based at their very lowest, the bottom basic level entirely on *Matrix and Vector Operations*; in all of our search engines ...

All of our internet banking, of our phoning operations etc. are ultimately *depending on Matrices and Vector Spaces* and *our coding and understanding thereof*.

Unfortunately (or luckily), the 'classically taught' first Linear Algebra courses are the most hated Math courses overall. That sad fact needs to be *remedied*.

Most of our early Linear Algebra courses are totally out of sync with after-Covid times where students had to learn quickly, by themselves or in spontaneous 'zoom' groups, what the majority of our standard Linear Algebra courses do not teach.

These 'classic' courses still rather rehash the highlights of the 18th and 19th century as their final 'summit' topics.

See the two before 1930 and after 1930 Linear Algebra subjects lists in the APPENDIX, on p. 28 and p. 29 and compare.

But *help is already on the way* in the form of *embedded grass-root advice* for *student use* in *all my seven Lesson Plans*.

This '*disconnect*' between *our modern needs* and the *classical discredited course contents* is the subject of this *Math Education paper*.

Trying to remedy and help all actors here.

Preamble

In East Asia's Taiwan and South Korea in 2014, I gave two separate talks at WONRA and ILAS Meetings on the history of Math Computations and on my current cluster of deep results in Matrix Theory and Matrix Computations from a new extraordinary rich cluster of Mathematical Research papers.

The Math Ed paper below addresses our elementary Linear Algebra teachings and deals with the globe-wide problem of "teaching for the test", mostly in 'top-down' lecturing.

Unfortunately we are generally not conveying Linear Algebra through interactive teaching methods, nor introducing modern Matrix Theory and Matrix Computational methods to our beginning students.

But Help is already on its way ...

Overcoming this dilemma is the most urgent task

in all of Mathematics

Today .

Are there *any problems* in our Linear Algebra teaching or teachings ?

In subjects taught, or ... where are our problems – if any ?

In Linear Algebra and Matrix Theory, what is wrong ?

Teaching and/or research wise ?

What needs to be done immediately ?

We must modernize our early College syllabi in Linear Algebra and enliven this area of Mathematics that helps us all so extraordinarily in our daily cell-phone and internet based lives and in our AI and engineering advances.

How do we, how do you mostly teach the beginners' linear algebra classes today?

Which *subjects* do we, you, and I teach ?

Using modern Matrix Theory based ideas *or* from a classical and algebraic standpoint ?

Top-down taught *or* taught interactively ?

These are *our most urgent questions* today ,

in All of Mathematics .

1 : Math Education today, or *the Necessity of Modernizing the First Linear Algebra Course via coherent Matrix Theory Based Lesson Plans*

Based on [37], this section looks at how and what is standardly taught in our first College or University Linear Algebra courses in the US, in Europe, and around the globe.

Historically speaking, Linear Algebra has had *two periods of great expansions*.

One was in the 19th century and another is going on right now, as this area of mathematics has gained great importance and is being rejuvenated by deep *changes in the subject matter and in our understandings* thereof since the 1950s, with the *advent of electronic computers*.

With *Covid*, we switched to mostly *on-line teaching*.

To get a feel for what is going on globe-wide, search any university website for Linear Algebra video resources and you will find that the majority of our subject's first College courses are given in 'Vorlesungs' style, 'top-down', with *little red dots running around pages*, on a screen or handy — with the instructor droning on, as she or he *reads out aloud* to the class or section.

Here the English word of 'lecture' is replaced by its German equivalent "Vorlesung" which literally means a 'reading' from a script or a book – or (with a *little red dot flickering* across the screen) – from a '*canned*' internet site.

The Vorlesungs-’readers’ now are mostly young Ph. Ds. or post-docs, or young faculty, who most often *lecture top-down on-line*, with *few interactive or inverse methods of teaching or learning* Linear Algebra.

They have succumbed to the *Semmelweis Syndrome*, unknowingly – and *knowing no better way than to teach as they were taught ...* , and how we were most likely taught ourselves, *decades and centuries ago, honoring our teachers ...* .

[Look up ’Ignaz Semmelweis’ who advocated hand-washing at childbirth to reduce infections and deaths at the two separate gynecological wards, one lead by midwives and the other by medical research gynecologists, at the Charité in Berlin around 1800. He could not convince his medical colleagues to wash their hands since it was not mandated in their educational and professional canons.]

What could have been wrong with this approach then?

There were about 5 times the childbirth and mothers deaths in the medical doctors lead gynecology ward than in the midwives one.

This is reflected in our *glaring ’defect’* in most *math educational systems*, nearly world wide : Most of us teach how we were taught by our teachers and thereby honor one of the Mosaic Ten Commandments, *to honor our parents or teachers.*

But we forget the other Commandment, namely *not to kill* which we do in our students’ growth and their wish to learn in the almost ubiquitous on-line, top-down Linear Algebra classes by on-line or in-class lecturing that make this course the *most hated* one of all mathematics courses in College.

This *defect* has to be *overcome quickly, like yesterday* in our early *Linear Algebra* courses; assuming that we want to give our first year elementary Linear Algebra students the *value education* that they *deserve, want, and need* today.

Linear Algebra now requires *alternate methods of teaching, modified subject lists* and *modern subject development methods* that are congruent with the modern uses of *Matrix Theory* and *Matrix Computations*.

Can we teach Linear Algebra in a new way?

What would that new way be?

Will 'any new way' succeed to *modernize our first Linear Algebra courses* soon enough and teach our students the *same subject matter*, but in a *modern, useful, and usable way*?

We must *adopt different ways to teach*.

The *times are ripe* for *on-line* and *interactive teaching*.

Here is our chance to veer off from our near universal practice of *learning* and thereby *teaching for a test*.

This has been the standard teaching practice for decades in US schools. And *since Pisa* it has *sadly* become the *global teaching norm* abroad as well.

The century old *Piaget principle* of how humans of all ages *learn deeply*, stipulates clearly that we *learn best* when we *want to learn* and *need to learn* for *our own enjoyment* and for *our own personal mental growth*.

Google 'Jean Piaget'. Jean lived and worked in Switzerland all of his life and do read some of his readily available books and talks. Here, *in elementary inversely taught classes* on Linear Algebra is our *chance to set this abomination right*.

Lesson Plans will generate true learning in our students.

They will set them free to use these skills in many other professions by learning about the *Art of Mathematics* – without becoming mathematicians themselves, unless they want to.

In our first Linear Algebra courses around the globe today, there are around 20 to 100 (\pm) times more students than 'teachers'.

Our students are hurt by most of us, as we are overwhelmingly still teaching the achievements of the 1800s through the early 2000s as our Linear Algebra courses' *highlights*.

The students suffer the most by our unfair and inadequate teaching methods (top-down lecturing, with centuries old 'highlights' and 'long discredited' nonsense).

Thus it is appropriate to engage the students to try and see them free themselves from this curse and its stifling teachings grip and thereby change their College teachers likewise. But how done ?

In East Asia and the US this summer I learnt that both teachers and their elementary Linear Algebra course students are becoming well aware of my *modern Lesson Plans*, their coherence and complete way to treat all standard subjects anew, but without any long discarded ballast of centuries ago. And I was very glad.

I call what is happening now world wide a ”**grass-roots fire**” that is fueled by the Post-Covid students themselves, ’a fire’ that will change the whole way in which we teach the elementary Linear Algebra course from now on and transform, see [26], it into a *modern Matrix* and *Matrix Computations* course in a few years – and hopefully even sooner.

My Lesson Plans create *critical thinkers, doers and citizens* –
in Piaget’s way.

I have seen this transformation in many of my interactively taught classes and regularly had my graduating students bring their parents to my office on Graduation Day, to see me who had given them their last C or C- for their learning efforts. Thereafter they had become an all As or Bs student, because *they had learnt to think and work by and for themselves*.

*’Vorlesungs’ style top-down lecturing,
even on-line, is clearly out.*

Matrix Theory can nowadays best be taught via *interactive teaching and learning about Matrices*.

Ideally I can envision an *on-line source of Lessons* that *students read and study first at home*, then *come to class to discuss and deepen each Lesson’s contents*.

With the teacher at hand, *studying in small groups* of 3 to 5 and 6 to 12 or 25 students in each group; working on several black- or white-boards, life or on-line, in *one classroom* on campus or on *Zoom*.

A *holistic analysis diagram* of our tasks in any first Linear Algebra course was given earlier in [37] and studied in several previous Linear Algebra education workshops around the globe.

Next we expand and explain the *holistic process* in 3 diagrams :

An attempt at a *basic holistic map* of the *spiderweb of forces* that govern our efforts to learn and to teach today in 2026. –

At its center : *the actors, you and I*

Learners and Teachers; *dwellers all, in time and space* [1] .

An attempt at a basic holistic map of the *spiderweb of forces* that govern our efforts to learn and teach *Mathematics* today in 2026.

At its center : the actors, *you and I* .

Learners and teachers; all combined .

[**How ? What ? When ? Why ?**]

The "Why"s, or our personal motivations and aims with teaching.

The "What" to teach, and the "When" to teach "What" and how.

[How ? What ? When ? Why ?]

The Pedagogy for today's students, given our current awareness and the need to teach interactively, with modern Matrix Computational Thoughts and Matrix Methods.

The [**How ? What ? When ? Why ?**]

All explained in one holistic diagram

Our *Linear Algebra Teaching Dilemma* today is presented clearly on the *two 'diagonal' arrow pairs* of the holistic diagrams above. Driven by the desire to *relieve the students' problems* depicted there, my *set of Lesson Plans* has been developed specifically for *interactive teaching* and for *inverse teaching methods*.

The Lesson Plans are freely available for all at

<https://la-education.oucreate.com/teaching-resources/lesson-plans/franks-lesson-plans/>.

The inverse teaching approach generally works wonders.

Usually my students become coaches and tutors after a few weeks for students in parallel elementary Linear Algebra classes that are taught in classical subjects textbook style, on-line or off.

A student income source and an early teaching experience.

The *Lesson Plans* point to *what we teach* our students from the *historic development of Mathematics* today.

Choosing between centuries old 'stuff' or 'modern' concepts.

This is affected by the *students' mental maturity level* – and by *our own awareness level* as instructors.

My *Lesson Plans* are designed to *help students and teacher* to *understand and appreciate the subjects* of our *classical algebraic first Linear Algebra curriculum* intuitively from the *most simple action* of *matrix \times vector multiplication*.

My seven Lesson Plans exemplify the role of Matrices and Linear Transformations in a *modern, fully and completely Matrix theoretical approach*.

It is well worth the reader's time to study the two historical lists in [37], re-printed below on pages 28 and 29 in an APPENDIX; and then try to *understand our current Teaching Dilemma* within our first Linear Algebra course and *its history*.

How would I teach a modern Linear Algebra course today ?

Given that I have recently completed this set of seven Lesson Plans that cover all subjects of a 'Classical' first Linear Algebra Course in 28 to 30 class days in a *modern, matrix based way*.

How would you ?

The Lesson Plans hinge on three fundamental processes :

(1) The *Row Echelon Form Reduction* allows us to *study all vector spaces, the intrinsic qualities of sets of vectors and the structure of linear vector-space relations*.

This is the subject of the first four Lesson Plans.

(2) Then *Krylov's Matrix \times Vector Iterations* [15] take over in the later Lesson Plans, when we are trying to understand the *intrinsic properties of matrices, i.e., their eigen structures*.

Both of these pivotal aspects of *modern Linear Algebra* rely on
(3) *Riesz' Standard Basis Matrix Representations* [20] of 1909 for *linear transformations f of n -space* that we encounter in the very first days of Lesson Plan 1.

My *Lesson Plans* are *uniformly built on Matrices* and on *modern Matrix Theory and Matrix Computations*.

My Lesson Plans *do not treat determinants*, they do not touch the characteristic polynomial or polynomial root finding, nor the unstable Gram-Schmidt orthonormal basis algorithms, see Nick Trefethen and David Bau [23], p. 50, or Gauss's ill-conditioned normal equation method of 1815, see Olga Taussky [21]; **nor** Cramer's determinantel rule from 1750, nor the rule of signs from the 16th or 15th century, or the Ruth-Hurwitz matrix stability formulas from around 1900.

The *knowledge base of the 19th century* or of the *early 1900s* is *not sufficient* for the demands of a *modern Linear Algebra syllabus*, nor does it introduce our students to the *modern uses of Linear Algebra and Matrices*.

The two lists in the APPENDIX show the achievements of developing Linear Algebra's more *abstract notions* in centuries past and in *modern matrix computations*, – the latter only possible *after the advent of electronic computers* in World War 2.

Our students, the client disciplines and colleagues generally welcome this *switch to modernity* because such Lesson Plans develop simple *modern Matrix Theory* and *Matrix Computational notions* that are *easy to grasp, to apply, to evaluate, to retain, and easy to teach*, and just as *easy to learn interactively*.

The first class notes of my Lesson Plan 1 on pages i through v and 1 through 11 set the *tone of the class* as interactive and *accepting all inputs graciously and encouragingly from students and teachers* alike.

These first classes are best set up as *inverse teaching exercises*, where *all actors have read and thought first* about the leading 16 pages of Lesson Plan 1 *by themselves* and then are *encouraged to talk about them freely* in class.

In fact, *the main aim of my Lesson Plan 1 is to encourage students and teachers* to contribute their *thoughts and ideas* freely and to *gladly share their understandings and mis-understandings of mathematical notions, practices or problems*, while ...

While - for example - *we construct a mathematical proof of Fred-eric Riesz's Representation Theorem from 1909 [20] for Linear Transforms f of \mathbb{R}^n or \mathbb{C}^n* in the *first few days* of Linear Algebra class, slowly guided from student input and coached by gentle instructors' help and advice, – (*but only when needed*).

This introduces the class to *inverse teaching* and *fosters their own thoughts and deep math learning* by following the *Piaget Principle's* way.

(This *exercise in abstraction* will help us later to study *matrix representations for arbitrary bases*, to understand '*basis change*', and then to work with *matrix eigenvalues* in Lesson Plan 5.)

But first, students have to understand how to *multiply matrices and vectors*, how to adhere to the "*row before column*" *notational rule* and understand the *dot product* of *row and column vectors*, and how to *multiply matrices and vectors* of *all compatible sizes* or '*dimensions*'.

Early on, we teach students and they learn how to *row reduce matrices by hand*. What happens to almost zero entries?

Then they create their own *row reduction* Matlab (or other *software*) codes. And later they learn about the *role* and the *effects* of *small, near zero pivots* in Lesson Plans 2 and 3.

In Lesson Plans 4 and 5 we introduce *Krylov Vector Iterations* [15] to find *invariant subspaces* under *linear transformations*, see [26], and *matrix eigenvectors*, as well as their *eigenvalues* constructively – without the *ballast from the 19th century* of determinants, characteristic polynomials, or polynomial root finding ...

These have been *completely impractical* since *their inception* by Augustin-Louis Cauchy et al., *three centuries ago*.

Long before the advent of *electronic Computers* and before *modern Numerical Analysis* was developed.

2 : Philosophical Remarks and Conclusions about the Genesis of our New Computational Results after Covid Times, a Metaphysical Outlook

Where will this desire for modernity in math all lead to.

Where will it end?

The universe, the Earth and those who live on Earth, humans and animals, plants and clouds, climate and societies, nations and social interactions are *constantly adapting* and *changing* and we and they have been changing for billions of years, *forwards and back*.

The universe is continually evolving and so are we.

That is life.

Why was I tempted to write and how did I actually come to write this meta-mathematical section upon solving these old and long abandoned fundamental math and science problems?

Next I will try to explain the genesis of this new interconnected and extraordinary cluster of mathematical thoughts and results – as best I can.

Something rarer and more special has been going on and affecting the Earth and our lives in the last couple of years.

Our minds and our individual and group consciousnesses have made leaps and bounds and we have bounced forward.

We have become *more awake spiritually*, within ourselves and of others.

We try to think '*equity and inclusion*' now.

At the same time we are *confronting our own demise*, threatened by *global epidemics*, through *overusing our resources* and by *environmental pollution*, by *needless consumption*, and affecting *our own survival* with *man-made climate change*.

In wars, started for *dubious reasons* and with *ill effects*.

And *genocide* is showing its face again around the globe.

We are still stewards of the Earth; *are we still?*

We are barely so.

How did this quite disparate research cluster come into being?

I feel that I am not, that *I was not* the *sole creator* here.

Besides my co-authors and colleagues and Linear Algebra's history, *some other force* was at work helping me, a *spiritual* or *karmic entity*, maybe *earthly* but most likely *otherwise*.

It drove me on, it sustained me, it has pushed me onwards for a long time, *for 60 years* or more, in and around Köln in Germany.

At first as a second year student at the University of Cologne, I was tasked to GTA a section of first year Linear Algebra students.

Thus I began to learn and think about how to teach at university. I did *gain my first experiences with interactive teaching of vectors and matrices* in Cologne in Mai 1965, as a *second year student of the subject* myself. And this approach would *follow me everywhere I went*.

As a student of Wolfram Jehne, Roland Burlisch, Manfred Lussem, Ulrich Trottenberg, Olga Taussky, John Todd, Alston Householder, Joseph Stoer, Fritz Reutter, Rolf Jeltsch, John Figgis Francis, Gene Golub, Peter Maxwell, Martin Gutknecht, Froilán Dopico, ,, , and of my students, and of many, many others.

Linear Algebra has *challenged me* in all of my *teachings* and in much of my *research life* since; see [26, Chapter 9.1], [27], [28], [29], [37] for some of my Math and Matrix Education papers.

There was a natural, broad support for me from Dorothy, my wife; from my family, my friends, from Sepideh, Rachel and Anthony of the ILAS Education committee and all of the International Linear Algebra Society (ILAS) itself.

And from the doctors who cured me of a deadly self-poisoning disease that affected me badly and could have killed me a couple of years ago.

But I survived and am now beginning to rehabilitate physically, – with thanks to many others who helped me and who are still helping me along the way.

And I still feel that something is missing from this description of these extraordinary events, namely

*The spiritual force that guarded and guided me
throughout my entire life.*

Let me admit and say clearly now that I was saved by my *Angel* who would not let me die with such great tasks and joys of discovery ahead.

These tasks are now done and I am very grateful.

Now I can dedicate myself again to my other creative outlet, *photographing the world as I see it* in my inner eye.

And also continue with math – on rainy days – or when I am called to Math, or with family work – and possibly to Teaching again.

May everyone find ways to listen to his or her mentors throughout their life and stay in touch with her or his Angel – and ultimately

fulfill their karmic tasks and work on Earth.

I wish you luck and health on your journey.

What brought on this extraordinary cluster of results, all nearly at once; such questions are open to interpretation and beyond the scope of this paper — and

well beyond this author's mind.

APPENDIX

Here we list named old, ancient and modern Linear Algebra subjects that are touched upon in most of our current elementary Linear Algebra textbooks and are generally taught or touched on in our current first elementary Linear Algebra courses.

The first list below summarized the achievements from the first expansion of Linear Algebra research in the eighteen and early nineteen hundreds.

Algebra and Linear Algebra notions developed before 1930

Gaussian elimination; Gaxby, Saxby	Assur and Babylon	4000 to 2000 BE	} Standard math contents with algebraic proofs or pencil and paper explanations in a majority of our current Linear Algebra textbooks and classes today.
polynomial	Descartes	1637	
polynomial roots			
complex numbers	Cardano	1545	
rule of signs	Descartes	1637	
matrix	Leibniz, Seki	1683	
determinant	Cardano, Seki, Leibniz	1545, 1683, 1693	
Cramer's rule	Cramer	1750	
fundamental theorem of algebra	Gauss	1799	
Cauchy-Schwarz inequality	Cauchy, Schwarz	1821, 1888	
normal equation	Gauss	1822	
Ruth-Hurwitz	Ruth, Hurwitz	1876, 1895	
Gram-Schmidt orthogonalization	Gram, Schmidt	1883, 1907	
eigenvector	Euler	1751, 1760	
eigenvalue	Cauchy	1819	
characteristic polynomial	Cauchy	1819	
Cayley-Hamilton theorem	Cayley, Hamilton	1858, 1864	
Jordan normal form	Jordan	1870	
Cholesky decomposition	Cholesky	1910	
Gershgorin Circles	Gershgorin	1931	
minimal polynomial	Krylov	1931	
vector iteration	Krylov	1931	

And here is a list of modern 20th and 21st century Linear Algebra subjects.

Linear Algebra concepts and notions developed after 1930

LR factorization	historic		
Schur decomposition	Schur	1909	
Gershgorin Circles	Gershgorin	1931	} Math items less emphasized in our teachings and textbooks. 'No time left' for most of these topics.
vector iteration	Krylov	1931	
vanishing polynomial	Krylov	1931	
partial column-pivoting	Cauer	1938	
Hessenberg matrix	Hessenberg	1943	
steepest descend, Conj. Grad.	Lanzcos, Hestenes	1949	
QR factorization	(Nat. Bureau of Stand.)	1950	
Givens reflection	Givens	1950	
Householder transform	Householder	1958	
QR algorithm	Francis, Kublanovskaya	1961	
singular value decomposition	Golub, Kahan	1965	
invariant subspace theory	Watkins	1980	
SVD, 'PageRank' search engine	Page, Brin	1996	
QR multi-shift algorithm	Braman, Byers, Mathias	2002	
TensorFlow search engine	Google team	2021	

In both lists, the golden 1800s and the modern 1930 + Linear Algebra lists, the works of Semyon Aronovich Gerschgorin (1901 – 1933) [9] and Alexsei Krylov (1863 – 1945) [15] are outliers of sorts.

Gerschgorin was a professor in Leningrad and Krylov was a naval engineer and applied mathematician in Saint Petersburg at the time of their matrix results.

Incidentally, Alexsei Krylov 'presented' S. Gerschgorin in 1917 before the Academy of Sciences. Their respective offices were adjacent, in the same building, from two separate Universities and Departments, in this doubly named city.

Their office building was quite near to and south of the Neva River, in the joint University Sector of Leningrad and Saint Petersburg. And the Neva still flows into the Baltic Sea there.

Historic Math confluences.

In 1931 Aleksei Krylov published his seminal paper [15] on Vector Iteration and Krylov Subspaces for square matrices $A_{k,k}$. The excerpts below from Krylov's paper, translated from Russian into English, can be found at

<https://mathshistory.st-andrews.ac.uk/Biographies/KrylovAleksei/>.

"It is clear that, if for $k = 2$ and $k = 3$ it is easy to compose this [secular] equation (i.e., the characteristic polynomial $f(x)$ of a k by k matrix), then for $k = 4$ the laying-out becomes cumbersome, and for values k more than 5 this is completely unrealizable in a direct way.

Therefore one should use methods where the full development of the determinant is avoided. The aim of the paper ... is to present simple methods of composition of the secular equation (i.e., the minimal polynomial) in the developed form, after which, its solution, i.e. numerical computation of its roots, does not present any difficulty".

Krylov's first paragraph above gives a realistic description of what the majority of our students today are tasked with, when trying to compute the characteristic equation of even very low dimensional square matrices $A_{k,k}$ by hand.

In almost all of our elementary first Linear Algebra classes and in our textbooks, students are still asked to repeat Krylov's low size matrix dilemma today.

This approach blocks a proper *Matrix Theoretical Understanding* of Matrix eigen-structures and eigen-behavior .

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